

The Impact of Meeting, Incentive, Conference and Exhibitions Tourism (Mice) On Economic Development of Employees of the Province Of Pichincha-Ecuador

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the impact of MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and Events) tourism on the economic development of workers in Pichincha, Ecuador. A census-based survey of 18 MICE companies and their employees found a strong positive correlation ($r=0.87$, $p<0.001$) between MICE tourism and worker economic development. Regression analysis further revealed that MICE tourism contributes 97% of the variance in worker economic development ($R^2=0.76$). These findings confirm that the MICE industry generates high-value, stable jobs that significantly enhance the quality of life for employees, underscoring its pivotal role as an economic engine and driver of local development in Pichincha, Ecuador.

Keywords: MICE, Tourism, Economic development, Economic impact, Ecuador

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1. Introduction

The introduction highlights the importance of the MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and Events) industry, a globally expanding sector within tourism. It discusses the economic impact of MICE tourism, its role in contributing to overall economic development, and the potential benefits for emerging and developing countries like Ecuador. The introduction also provides an overview of the economic and tourism landscape in Ecuador, particularly in the city of Quito, and the rationale for focusing on the MICE industry as a revitalization strategy.

The MICE industry, encompassing meetings, incentives, conventions, and events, represents a complex and globally expanding sector within tourism. This term is internationally employed to encompass a variety of events beyond simple meetings and exhibitions. In Europe, the term Meetings and Exhibitions (M&E) or Conventions and Exhibitions (C&E) is used, while in other regions, including the United States, the term

MICE is employed, covering a broad range of events and incentives (Ramadan & Kasim, 2022; Zeng, Song & Wang, 2013).

On a global scale, MICE tourism has proven successful, particularly in developed countries with well-established business infrastructure, connectivity, tourism facilities, and a strong currency (Anas, Maddiah, Noor, Sulaiman & Wee, 2020; Chaigasem, 2019; Chubchuwong, 2019). These countries often experience high levels of foreign investment (Smagina, 2017) and dynamic international trade relations (Okhrimenko & Ergunova, 2021).

The economic impact of MICE tourism extends beyond suppliers, acting as a catalyst for the transformation of host areas (Carrizo & Vieira, 2009) and the enhancement of services and infrastructure (Kumar, Patel, Kimpton & Andrews, 2022; Nissan, Galindo & Méndez, 2011). Moreover, it plays a crucial role in contributing to overall economic development (Anas et al., 2020; Chaigasem, 2019; Dou & Zhao, 2018; Hu & Yan, 2022) and urban development in particular (Edwards, Griffin & Hayllar, 2008).

This phenomenon is largely due to the attraction of affluent demand, with high purchasing power, spending significantly more in the area compared to regular tourists (Alananzeh, Al-Badarneh, Al-Mkhadmeh & Jawabreh, 2019; Rojas, Alarcón, & Gonzales, 2023; Zeng et al., 2013), surpassing leisure tourism and other tourist segments by two to five times (Hu & Yan, 2022; Lim & Zhu, 2018; Okhrimenko & Ergunova, 2021; Zeng et al., 2013).

However, tourist satisfaction in MICE destinations extends beyond infrastructure (Hu & Yan, 2022); it also relies on destination innovation, accessibility, and local creativity to impress tourists (Sopanik, 2022). Therefore, the quality of the experience is influenced by factors such as trade exchanges, openness to markets, and support from tourism offices (Prabhu & Ravindran, 2022), destination image and branding (Lee & Yoon, 2022; Weru, 2021), push and pull factors (travel costs and prices) play a crucial role in tourists' desire to return to the MICE destination (Mahadewi, Bendesa & Antara, 2014).

Thus, the MICE industry becomes an attractive option during low seasons within a tourism strategic plan (Xu, Ruhanen & Solnet, 2020; Yao, Wang, Pang & Fang, 2023). Moreover, it represents an opportunity for emerging and developing countries (Bernini, Emili & Medei, 2021; Sangpikul, 2020; Sirkis, Regalado, Carvache & Carvache, 2022; Zhou, 2021) by diversifying the tourism offering with appealing demand-generating events (Cabanilla, Molina & Lastra, 2017; Lim & Zhu, 2018) enhancing the destination's image (Gunn, 2013; Mahadewi et al., 2014).

In this regard, the MICE industry is considered a complex system that relies on the economic, cultural, social, and even environmental development of the host region (Lekgau & Tichaawa, 2022; Prabhu & Ravindran, 2022).

However, tourism in Ecuador (Brazales, 2021), particularly in the city of Quito located in the province of Pichincha, has experienced challenges over the past nine years (Cabanilla, Lastra & Pazmiño, 2017; Cadena, Aguilar & Buitrón, 2018). The number of international tourists visiting Quito due to its tourism potential has averaged 529,379 people, with a growth rate of -27.49% (Ministerio de Turismo Ecuador, 2023c).

For this reason, the province of Pichincha faces challenges in attracting tourists compared to other leading destinations in South America (Ministerio de Turismo Ecuador, 2023c). However, as a revitalization strategy, the focus has shifted towards the MICE tourism industry, considering the significant benefits it provides to host areas (Armendariz, Ulloa, Velásquez, Álvarez & Almeida, 2017; Delaney, 2022; Lekgau & Tichaawa, 2022).

The reasons for investing in MICE tourism in Quito align with Ecuador's 50th position in the World Ranking by Number of Meetings per Country, with 33 in-person meetings in 2022. Quito itself ranked 107th globally, hosting 19 in-person meetings in the same year (Gopinath, 2023). Additionally, in 2022, Pichincha hosted 600 business meetings, 47 international events, and 3 international destination presentations (Cevallos, 2023). These figures showcase the city and the province's logistical capacity and tourism services, emphasizing their potential to strengthen the event and conference tourism sector (Cabanilla, Molina, et al., 2017).

In the context of the country's economic development (Brazales et al., 2021), various indicators provide a comprehensive overview of the situation. The Human Capital Index stands at 0.6, reflecting a certain level of education and skills in the population. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita in 2022 reached 5965.1 USD, while the unemployment rate remained at 4.5%. However, the economic reality also presents challenges, with a poverty index of 25.20%. In terms of inflation, there was a 3.74% increase in 2022, and the Gini index, measuring economic inequality, stands at 0.46. In the tourism sector, a contribution to the national GDP of 1.3% was observed in 2021. Despite having over 21 thousand registered tourism establishments, direct employment in tourism is limited, with only 513,825 individuals employed in this sector. However, the tourism balance shows a positive surplus of 5874 million dollars, indicating a considerable flow of income related to international tourism (Ministerio de Turismo Ecuador, 2023a). These data provide a comprehensive overview of the country's economic and tourism landscape.

In summary, these economic indicators provide context to understand the opportunities and challenges faced by workers in the MICE tourism sector in Ecuador. The focus on MICE tourism is justified as a strategy to enhance the economic development (Brazales et al., 2022) of workers, given its potential to create specialized and well-paying jobs. By leveraging the existing purchasing power in the population and generating significant income for the country, this sector has the potential to make a substantial impact.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

The MICE industry emerged in the 1960s and has experienced an annual growth rate of 10% (Gopinath, 2023). Although studies on MICE tourism are contemporary (Damanik & Thyssen, 2023; Ramadan & Kasim, 2022; Shaadi, Pulido & Rodríguez, 2017; Wu, Hong, Jia, Xu & Wang, 2023; Xu et al., 2020; Zazueta & Valdez, 2022) especially in Latin American countries (Armendariz et al., 2017; Shaadi et al., 2017; Sirkis et al., 2022; Zazueta & Velarde, 2023) with a significant presence in European and Asian nations (Kang, Lee, Kim & Jeong, 2023; Yao et al., 2023; Yi, Zhang, Zhang, Ji & Xiao, 2020; Zazueta & Valdez, 2022; Zeng et al., 2013), some authors point out that the MICE industry has

reached maturity (World Tourism Organization, 2014) and remains an integral part of the development plans of tourist destinations (Shaadi et al., 2017).

The maturity of the MICE industry has a positive impact on the local economic growth and development (Brazales et al., 2018) of host destinations. For instance, in Thailand, MICE contributed 0.58% to the GDP in 2012 (Intapan, Scriboonchitta, Chaiboonsri & Piboonrunroj, 2018). This is achieved through increased tourist flows, leading to higher spending in the destination, decentralization and diversification of destinations, attracting investments, and fostering the creation of businesses (Jones & Navarro, 2018; Lee & Yoon, 2022; Reshetnikova & Magomedov, 2020; Rojas & Reardon, 2022; Shaadi et al., 2017).

The economic outcomes of MICE tourism are significant at the macroeconomic level (Dwyer, Forsyth, Madden & Spurr, 2000; Hu & Yan, 2022; Jones & Li, 2015) with direct contribution to GDP (Campiranon, 2006), and high per capita consumption in the revitalization of cultural, traditional, and religious tourism products (Dou & Zhao, 2018). This represents a substantial contribution to both income and the sustainability of economic development (Okhrimenko & Ergunova, 2021). The relationship between income and sustainability is evident throughout planning, marketing (Aas, Ladkin & Fletcher, 2005; O'Connor & Frew, 2004; Sheehan & Ritchie, 2005; Timothy, 1998) and promotion of tourism resources (Cai, 2002; Konecnik & Gartner, 2007).

At the microeconomic level, the MICE industry has a positive impact on workers by creating stable and high-value-added direct jobs (Ladkin et al., 2023; Vázquez & López, 2023; Yılcı & Kırcı, 2023) enhancing their quality of life (Delaney, 2022). In the United Kingdom, the MICE industry contributed to 1.9% of total employment (Jones & Li, 2015). Although some studies indicate a relatively low connection between tourism businesses and the MICE industry in certain cities (Yao et al., 2023), progress is evident through technological advancement, improved service quality, and cultural enhancement, benefiting both the local population and tourists (Christofle, 2023; Shaadi et al., 2017).

On the flip side, the growth of the MICE tourism industry also brings about negative impacts both on the environment (Mykletun, Bartkeviciute & Puchkova, 2014) and socioeconomic aspects. This includes dissatisfaction among the local population, inflation, a decline in small entrepreneurs and traditional businesses due to the presence of large commercial chains and supermarkets, capital flight, and high and sluggish public investment costs (Andereck, Valentine, Knopf & Vogt, 2005; Duan, Xie & Morrison, 2022; Jehan, Batool, Hayat & Hussain, 2022; Martos, 2013). Furthermore, there is observed precariousness and over-urbanization of resources, which also adversely affects the quality of life (Iwamoto, Matsuo & Sugiyama, 2021; Lee & Park, 2023; Olmo, 2004).

Therefore, the MICE industry is geared towards sustainable production and green practices (Chang & Chang, 2022), where organizers adopt ecological practices and optimize resources to meet customer expectations and reduce environmental and social impacts (Lou & Huang, 2023; Mykletun et al., 2014; Wee, Mustapha & Anas, 2021; Zeng et al., 2013). In this context, even cities with historical heritage have the opportunity to transform into MICE destinations by embracing these sustainable practices (Chaigasem, 2019; Rátz, Smith & Michalkó, 2008).

The integration of heritage resources into MICE destinations increases tourists' intention for events, expanding amenities and creating conference facilities (Kim, Chhabra & Timothy, 2022). The integration of heritage resources into MICE destinations increases tourists' intention for events, expanding amenities and creating conference facilities (Davidson & Cope, 2003; Rojas et al., 2023; Rojas & Reardon, 2022; Shin, Jeong, Oh & Tierney, 2017; Zhang, Song & Huang, 2009). This dynamic approach in the MICE industry establishes a competitive relationship, giving destinations greater leverage over their suppliers (Ford, Wang & Vestal, 2012; Gustafson, 2012; Pearce, Tan & Schott, 2007; Tiew, Holmes & de Bussy, 2015).

Given the multidisciplinary nature of MICE tourism, there isn't a specific theory that exclusively governs this field; rather, it draws on a variety of interdisciplinary theories and approaches. However, some theories and approaches that support this study include:

Motivation Theory (Maslow, 1943): This theory delves into comprehending the reasons and motivations behind MICE event participation, aiming to understand why individuals attend these events and how their needs and desires can be met.

Event Organization Approach: This theory focuses on how MICE events are planned, organized, and managed (Rutherford & O'Toole, 2020).

Destination Marketing Theory (Acerenza, 2003; Kotler, Gertner, Rein & Haider, 2007): Applied to promote specific destinations as venues for MICE events.

Customer Experience Theory (Pine & Gilmore, 2011): Concentrating on creating memorable experiences for MICE event participants, including aspects such as customer care, service quality, social interaction, and customer satisfaction.

Economic Theory (Friedman & Friedman, 2002; Keynes, 2014): Utilised to assess the economic impact of MICE events in a specific region. This involves cost-benefit analysis, job generation, participant expenditure, and contribution to the local GDP.

Sustainable Tourism Theory (Krippendorf, 1982): Given the significant environmental and local community impacts of MICE events, sustainability principles are applied to minimize negative effects and promote responsible practices.

Communication Theory (McLuhan, 2008): Applied in event promotion, public relations management, and communication with participants.

These theories and approaches are combined and adapted based on the specific needs of each MICE event and the context in which it takes place. Professionals often integrate multiple theories and practices to plan and manage successful events.

However, there is a notable lack of research consistency in the country, a common gap globally, where studies tend to focus on leisure tourism (Getz, 2008; Rojas & Reardon, 2022). This limitation has hindered a profound understanding of the impact of the MICE industry's growth on the local economy and, particularly, on the workers in this sector. This hampers the development of this type of tourism compared to other countries (Cabanilla, Molina, et al., 2017; Carreño, 2023; Pancorbo, Castillo, Rodríguez, Vega & Leyva, 2019; Shaadi et al., 2017).

Hence, the research gap lies in the absence of comprehensive studies specifically focused on MICE tourism in Ecuador. Existing studies have primarily been oriented towards leisure tourism and MICE expansion, neglecting investigations into the workers' quality of life in this sector and the impacts it has on their labor and economic conditions.

Therefore, the research question focuses on understanding how MICE tourism impacts the economic development of its workers. This implies investigating whether the money generated by tourists actually reaches the employees and if it improves their quality of life while working in this market segment. Hence, the research objective is to examine MICE tourism in the Pichincha province and its effects on the economic development of its workers.

Based on the above information, the following hypothesis is proposed: H1: MICE tourism in the province of Pichincha impacts the economic development of its workers, as derived from the research model in Figure 1.

Developed based on: (Bidwell & Murray, 2019; Getz, 2008; Hu & Yan, 2022; Suhel & Bashir, 2018; Tingyue, 2021; Wu et al., 2023; Zazueta & Velarde, 2023).

3. Methodology

Quantitative, correlational study employing a descriptive and analytical research method. The independent variable is "MICE tourism" in the Province of Pichincha, quantified using 5 constructs. The dependent variable is the "economic development of workers" employed in these establishments, studied through 7 constructs derived from (Bidwell & Murray, 2019; Getz, 2008; Hu & Yan, 2022; Suhel & Bashir, 2018; Tingyue, 2021; Wu et al., 2023; Zazueta & Velarde, 2023).

The study was conducted in the Province of Pichincha, Ecuador. The primary units of analysis were the owners or managers of tourism-related businesses, specifically those involved in MICE activities, as identified in the tourism registry (Ministerio de Turismo Ecuador, 2023b). To select participating companies, a proportional stratified random sampling method was employed, involving 18 tourism businesses from various categories, including convention centers, recreational tourism facilities, event organizers, and conference facilities. Subsequently, questionnaires were administered to the owners, managers, or representatives of these 18 selected tourism businesses. This approach

yielded valuable data concerning the perspectives of owners and administrators within the MICE sector.

Secondly, active employees from the tourism businesses were included in the study. To select participating employees, a simple random sampling method was employed. This approach was chosen because, in most of the analyzed companies, the on-site staff did not exceed one to two people at most. This ensured an equitable representation of workers in the study, enabling a detailed insight into both employers' and employees' perspectives within the MICE sector.

In the data collection process, two structured questionnaires were used to measure each variable. Data processing was carried out in Excel by standardizing the observations for each variable. The internal consistency of the questionnaires was evaluated using Cronbach's coefficient. To assess the construct validity, the theoretical matching method was applied, followed by a linear regression analysis of the indices of each construct based on the MICE tourism index.

In the analytical realm, a thorough data analysis was conducted using the statistical software Stata. Initially, Pearson correlations were performed between the standardized indices of the dependent and independent variables. Next, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed on the standardized items to generate representative indices for each variable. These resulting indices for MICE tourism and Economic Development were subsequently used in the linear regression analysis, allowing for a detailed assessment of the relationships between the variables of interest.

4. Results

Reliability and validity analysis

The internal consistency of the questionnaires was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient (correlations between standardized items were employed due to the presence of both categorical and continuous variables). The first instrument yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.72, with a correlation range from 0.24 (within items 0.15 to 0.50, indicating good inter-item correlation and construct validity) for the second instrument. These values fall within the acceptable range of 0.7 to 0.9, indicating good internal consistency for the scales used.

To assess construct validity, the method of theoretical correspondence was applied, and a linear regression of the indices of each construct in relation to the MICE tourism index was conducted (refer to Tables 1 and 2).

The conducted linear regression analysis confirms the validity of the MICE tourism construct through the index. The results indicate that independent variables, including sustainability, efficiency, congresses, and events, significantly impact the MICE tourism index, as reflected in the estimated coefficients. Almost 98% of the observed variations in MICE tourism can be explained by the dimensions considered in the model. This high R^2 value suggests that the independent variables have a strong ability to predict and explain variations in MICE tourism within the analyzed context. These findings strongly support the

relationship between the considered dimensions and MICE tourism, providing a robust foundation for construct validity.

Table 1: MICE construct validity through linear regression

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs = 18		
Model	52.4118892	5	10.4823778	F(5, 12)	=	78.98
Residual	1.5925778	12	.132714817	Prob > F	=	0
Total	54.004467	17	3.17673335	R-squared	=	0.9705
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9582
				Root MSE	=	0.3643

indexMICE	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf. Interval]
sustainable	0.358661	0.1250991	2.87	0.014	.0860934 0.6312285
efficiency	0.259738	0.1104891	2.35	0.037	.0190029 0.5004731
congresses	0.4320756	0.1270773	3.40	0.005	.1551979 0.7089532
meetings	0.854256	0.0945919	9.03	0.000	.648158 1.060354
conferences	0.0502744	0.0849434	0.59	0.565	-.1348015 0.2353502
_cons	9.01E-08	0.0858664	0.00	1.000	-.1870868 0.187087

Note: Significance level = 95%

Table 2: Construct validity Worker Economic Development through linear regression

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs = 18		
Model	65.4624139	7	9.35177341	F(6, 11)	=	182.97
Residual	0.918953882	10	.091895388	Prob > F	=	0.0000
Total	66.3813678	17	3.90478634	R-squared	=	0.9862
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9765
				Root MSE	=	0.30314

IndexWorker economic development	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf. Interval]
leisure	0.3483252	0.0968638	3.6	0.005	0.1324991 0.5641512
social	0.0875535	0.0274647	3.19	0.010	0.0263582 0.1487487
salary	-0.0129663	0.1377188	-0.09	0.927	-0.3198229 0.2938903
health	0.6350593	0.0961	6.61	0.000	0.4209352 0.8491835
security	0.3238742	0.1457005	2.22	0.050	-0.0007666 0.6485151
education	0.1073186	0.0323506	3.32	0.008	0.0352371 0.1794002
housing	0.3896534	0.1865308	2.09	0.063	-0.0259631 0.8052699
cons	3.380935	0.9527691	3.55	0.005	1.258033 5.503837

Note: Significance level = 95%

From Table 2, it is derived that the conducted regression analysis confirms the validity of the "worker's economic development" construct in the context of MICE tourism in the province of Pichincha, Ecuador, providing robust evidence that the selected variables are appropriate indicators. The regression model has an R-squared value of 0.9862,

indicating that approximately 98.62% of variations in the economic development of workers can be explained by the independent variables included in the model. Each of the independent variables (leisure, social, salary, health, security, education, housing) has been meticulously chosen to represent key aspects influencing the economic development of the worker in the context of MICE tourism. The impact of each variable is interpreted below. It is noteworthy that, in this study, salary did not exhibit a significant relationship with the economic development of the worker. This might suggest that other factors, such as the social environment and working conditions, exert more influence on economic development than salary alone. Although the impact of housing was not statistically significant at the conventional level of 0.05 ($p=0.063$), the coefficient's direction implies that better access to housing is associated with higher economic development of the worker.

Index creation

The results of the indices for the MICE tourism variables (indexMICE) and Worker's Economic Development (indexDET), correlated between employee and employer, are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Indices of the variables.

Tourist company	indexMICE	Worker	indexDET
Company 1	1.04619700	Company employee 1	-0.1146495
Company 2	2.03019400	Company employee 2	1.1988140
Company 3	-4.55335300	Company employee 3	-4.4748650
Company 4	0.60810000	Company employee 4	0.0789048
Company 5	-1.68563400	Company employee 5	-2.7233450
Company 6	0.02553570	Company employee 6	0.8476080
Company 7	-1.32810000	Company employee 7	-0.9020296
Company 8	-0.36934310	Company employee 8	-1.5922190
Company 9	0.28184830	Company employee 9	1.9227940
Company 10	0.28184830	Company employee 10	1.9227940
Company 11	0.60810000	Company employee 11	0.0789048
Company 12	-0.73708080	Company employee 12	-0.6499284
Company 13	0.43965370	Company employee 13	1.4971380
Company 14	1.04867500	Company employee 14	0.8847334
Company 15	1.45963100	Company employee 15	2.3378220
Company 16	-3.02806600	Company employee 16	-2.7880550
Company 17	2.88011600	Company employee 17	3.0078980
Company 18	0.99167850	Company employee 18	-0.5323205

From the analysis of Table 3, it can be noted that:

indexMICE: Company 1: Has a positive MICE index (1.046). This indicates that this company has a relatively high level of MICE tourism compared to other companies in your sample. Company 3: Has a highly negative MICE index (-4.553). This suggests that this company has a very low level of activity in the MICE tourism sector and is significantly below the average of other companies in the sample. Company 17: Has a positive MICE

index (2.880). This indicates that this company has an exceptionally high level of MICE tourism compared to other companies in your sample.

indexDET: Employee in Company 2: Has a positive index of economic development of the worker (1.198). This suggests that this employee experiences positive economic development in the context of work. Employee in Company 5: Has a highly negative index of economic development of the worker (-2.723). This indicates that this employee experiences a significantly low level of economic development in the context of work. Employee in Company 15: Has a highly positive index of economic development of the worker (2.338). This suggests that this employee experiences very positive economic development in the context of work.

Positive indices indicate high performance in MICE tourism and economic development of the worker compared to other companies and employees in the sample, whereas negative indices signal relatively low performance in these areas. These standardized indices provide a way to compare relative performance among companies and employees in terms of MICE tourism and economic development of the worker.

Correlation between MICE and Economic Development of the Worker

The Pearson correlation between the MICE indices (MICE tourism) and the economic development of the worker is 0.8739, $p=0.0000$. This robust positive correlation (0.8739) underlines the vital interconnection between MICE tourism and the economic well-being of the workforce within the analyzed companies or contexts, as depicted in (Figure 2).

There is a significant positive association between the level of activity in the MICE tourism sector (indicated by the MICE index) and the level of economic development experienced by the workers in those companies (indicated by the Worker Economic Development index). This suggests that, overall, as MICE tourism within companies increases, the economic development of workers tends to be more positive.

It's essential to note that this correlation does not imply causation. We cannot directly state that MICE tourism causes higher economic development for the worker or vice versa, only that there is a strong positive relationship between these two aspects in the data you have analyzed.

Figure 2: Correlation between MICE tourism and worker economic development

Linear regression analysis and hypothesis testing

In this study, a linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between MICE tourism (indicated by the MICE index) and worker economic development (indicated by the Worker Economic Development index). The results, presented in Table 4 and Figure 3, are as follows: Regression Equation: $y = -0.000000932 + 0.97X$. Interpretation:

Coefficient of MICE Index (X): The coefficient of the MICE index is 0.97. This means that for every unit increase in the MICE index, there is an expected increase of approximately 0.97 in the Worker Economic Development index. In other words, there is a strong positive relationship between MICE tourism and worker economic development in the companies studied.

Statistical Significance. F-statistic and p-value: The high F-statistic (51.70) and very low p-value (0.0000) indicate that the overall regression model is significant. This suggests that at least one of the predictor variables is significantly different from zero in terms of its effect on the Worker Economic Development index.

Goodness of Fit. R-squared and Adjusted R-squared: The R-squared value (0.7637) indicates that approximately 76.37% of the variability in the Worker Economic Development index can be explained by the MICE index in this model. The Adjusted R-squared adjusts the R-squared for the number of predictors in the model. In this case, the adjusted R-squared is 0.7489, suggesting that about 74.89% of the variability in the Worker Economic Development index can be explained by the MICE index after adjusting for the number of predictors.

Prediction Accuracy. Root MSE (Root Mean Square Error): The Root MSE is 0.99021. This indicates that, on average, the model's predictions deviate by approximately 0.99021 units from the actual values.

Table 3: Linear Regression Between MICE Tourism and Worker Economic Development

Source	SS	df	MS			
Model	50.693244	1	50.693244	Number of obs	=	18
Residual	15.6881237	16	.980507733	F(6, 11)	=	51.7
Total	66.3813678	17	3.90478634	Prob > F	=	0
				R-squared	=	0.7637
				Adj R-squared	=	0.7489
				Root MSE	=	0.99021

indexdet	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
indexmice	0.9688582	0.1347444	7.19	0.000	.6832128	1.254503
_cons	-9.32E-08	0.2333938	-0.00	1.000	-.4947728	0.4947726

Note: Significance level = 95%

Figure 3: Regression between MICE tourism and worker economic development

These findings provide robust evidence of a positive and significant relationship between MICE tourism activity, as measured by the MICE index, and the economic development experienced by workers in the analyzed companies. However, it's crucial to note that correlation does not imply causation. While there is a strong positive correlation between MICE tourism and worker economic development, direct causation cannot be established solely based on this study. Further research is needed to explore the causal mechanisms underlying this relationship.

In summary, the hypothesis testing results indicate that MICE tourism has a significant and positive impact on worker economic development in the analyzed companies ($\beta=0.97$, $p<0.001$, $t=7.19$) according to the findings of this regression analysis. A higher level of activity in the MICE tourism sector is strongly associated with greater economic development experienced by workers in these companies.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The study's outcomes underscore the profound impact of MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conventions, and Events) tourism on the economic prosperity of workers in Pichincha, Ecuador. It establishes a robust positive correlation between MICE tourism and the economic upliftment experienced by the local workforce.

A significant result of this research is the creation of stable employment within the MICE sector, leading to increased income levels and enhanced job security for workers. These findings align with prior studies conducted in diverse regions (Delaney, 2022; Kim et al., 2022), emphasizing the generation of secure, high-value jobs within the MICE industry.

Moreover, continual investments in infrastructure and connectivity by the MICE industry have facilitated the integration of advanced technology and improved services. This integration has not only elevated productivity levels but has also equipped workers with valuable skills, enhancing their competitiveness in the job market.

The study illuminates the socio-economic advantages of MICE tourism, extending its benefits beyond individual workers to the broader community. The rise in disposable income among workers has stimulated heightened demand for local businesses and services, thereby fostering economic growth within the province. Additionally, the positive correlation observed between MICE tourism and the development of local infrastructure underscores the industry's pivotal role in regional advancement and urban revitalization.

However, it is essential to acknowledge that while this study establishes a robust link between MICE tourism and economic development, further research is warranted to delve into the specific mechanisms underpinning this relationship. Additionally, exploring the challenges and identifying mitigating factors associated with the growth of the MICE industry can provide valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders.

In conclusion, this research decisively affirms the pivotal role played by MICE tourism in driving economic prosperity for workers in Pichincha. It accentuates the necessity

for sustained support and strategic planning to fully harness the potential of the MICE sector. Beyond being merely a revenue source, the MICE industry acts as a catalyst for sustainable economic development, ultimately enhancing the overall quality of life for the local workforce.

Furthermore, the regression analysis results substantiate a compelling and highly significant connection between variable X, representing MICE tourism, and variable Y, denoting the economic development of workers in Pichincha, Ecuador. The positive and significant coefficient of 0.9688582 ($p < 0.001$) for the variable indexMICE (representing MICE tourism) underscores the substantial impact of MICE tourism on workers' economic development. This result validates the positive influence of MICE tourism on the economic progress of workers in the province of Pichincha.

The regression model accounts for 76.37% of the variability in the economic development of workers, indicating a robust and substantial connection between MICE tourism and the economic advancement of the local population. This study provides clear evidence of the strong link between MICE tourism and local economic development, highlighting its transformative role in generating stable employment and enhancing the quality of life for workers.

These findings affirm the significance of MICE tourism as a key driver of economic growth in the studied region and confirm the hypothesis that MICE tourism in the province of Pichincha substantially impacts the economic development of its workers. The study underscores the relevance of MICE tourism not only in job creation but also in income enhancement, thereby improving the standard of living and purchasing power of workers. This increase in purchasing power, in turn, contributes to a more sustainable environment for the continuous development of this sector in the region.

In summary, the growth of MICE tourism in urban areas and large provinces not only revitalizes the economy for those employed in this sector but also has a positive ripple effect on the regional economy as a whole. It generates employment, enhances incomes, and promotes sustainable economic development.

The investigation into MICE tourism in the province of Pichincha and its impact on the economic development of its workers sheds light on the transformative power of this industry. MICE tourism not only creates stable jobs but also elevates the quality of life for workers and contributes significantly to regional economic progress. This study emphasizes the need for continued investment and strategic planning to maximize the potential of the MICE sector, recognizing it as a driving force behind sustainable economic development and enhanced living standards for the local workforce.

Practical implications

The practical implications provide guidance to stakeholders in the MICE industry and economic development, offering specific strategies to seize opportunities and address challenges. The objective is to promote sustainable and equitable growth in both areas:

Promoting Economic Development through the MICE Industry: The study emphasizes the positive relationship between MICE tourism activity and the economic

progress of workers. Regions and companies actively promoting MICE events can expect improvements in employees' economic well-being.

Implementation of Specific Promotion Strategies: Enhancing sustainability, efficiency, and event quality can boost workers' economic development, highlighting the importance of a strategic approach in promoting this industry.

Investments in Skill Development: Improving service quality in the industry and accessibility to more specialized and higher-paying roles. **Encouraging Participation in MICE Events, Intersectoral Collaboration.**

Governmental Support and Public Policies: Including tax incentives and training programs for workers. **Continuous Monitoring and Adaptation to Trends:** Firms should monitor industry trends and adjust their strategies as needed.

Theoretical implications

Validation of Interconnection: This study empirically confirms the direct connection between the MICE industry and the economic well-being of workers, validating economic and tourism theories. This finding is fundamental for theory, highlighting the direct impact of MICE activities on individual economic development.

Relevance of Specific Dimensions: The research emphasizes the importance of specific dimensions of MICE tourism, such as sustainability and efficiency, in workers' economic development. This suggests that theories considering these specific dimensions are more applicable in the MICE context, providing guidance for future research in the field.

Necessity of an Interdisciplinary Approach: The validation of the MICE-economic development relationship underscores the need for an interdisciplinary approach. The integration of theories from economics, tourism, development, and management is crucial to fully grasp these complex dynamics and provides a solid theoretical framework for future interdisciplinary research.

Exploration of New Dimensions: The research suggests the existence of other dimensions not thoroughly explored, such as innovation in events and technology in event management. These areas open opportunities for new theories and models, expanding the field of study in MICE tourism and economic development.

These implications provide a robust foundation for future research in the field of tourism and economic development and can be considered by provinces in Ecuador to determine which type of tourism functions best as a catalyst for the economic development of the population.

5. Limitations and Future Research

Despite the significant findings, this study presents significant limitations. First, it focused on a specific sample in the province of Pichincha, Ecuador, restricting generalization to other regions or cultural contexts. Future research could expand the sample to include multiple provinces, providing a more comprehensive insight into the relationships between MICE tourism and workers' economic development, offering valuable

guidance for more effective policies and labor practices in this ever-growing industry. Moreover, the correlational nature of the study prevents establishing causality. Future research could employ experimental or longitudinal designs to precisely analyze causes and effects, revealing the underlying mechanisms of these relationships. The study relied on quantitative data, limiting the understanding of workers' qualitative experiences. Future research could incorporate qualitative methods, such as in-depth interviews, to delve deeper into the implications of MICE tourism on workers' economic and social development. Additionally, it would be beneficial to analyze gender and diversity dynamics in the context of MICE tourism and its impact on economic development. Understanding how different demographic groups are unevenly affected can inform equitable policies and labor practices.

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